

Congo Red Complexes with Some Rare-Earth Salts

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Congo red forms brick red coloured water insoluble complexes with the chlorides of lanthanum, cerium, praseodymium, neodymium, samarium, gadolinium and dysprosium in aqueous solution at feebly acidic pH of 6.5. They have been studied in water medium at pH 6.5 conductometrically and their complexes have been isolated and analysed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Congo red (BDH grade) was dissolved in water to make 0.01*M* solution. The rare-earth salts solutions were made as mentioned in earlier works¹. The pH of water used all along the experiments were adjusted to 6.5 by the addition of requisite quantity of dilute hydrochloric acid.

Philips conductivity Bridge Model (PR 9500) was used for both direct and reverse conductometric titrations. The concentration of the solutions used were of the order of $0.5-1 \times 10^{-3}M$ to $0.5-1 \times 10^{-2}M$.

0.01*M* solution of congo red and a rare earth salt (La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd and Dy) in water was mixed in equal proportion and the precipitate thus obtained was separated by centrifugation, washed with water and alcohol, and dried in vacuum over quick-lime at room temp. of 30°. Microanalysis for the determination of carbon, sulphur, nitrogen and hydrogen was done by the courtesy of Micro Analytical Service, Melbourne, Australia. For the analysis of the metal the complex was fused with fusion mixture in a platinum crucible and the fused mass was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and the rare earth estimated².

For the estimation of chloride the fused mass as above was dissolved in dilute nitric acid and the chloride was estimated as silverchloride³. The results of analysis is given in Table 1.

1. *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 444.
2. J. F. Spencer. "The Metals of the rare-earths", Longmans, Green and Co., London, 1919, p. 105.
3. A. I. Vogel. A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis including the Elementary Instrumental Analysis. The English Language Book Society and Longmans, Green and Co. Ltd., 1962, p. 460.

TABLE 1,

Congo red complexes with rare-earth salts

	metal	C	N	H	S	Cl
1. <i>Lanthanum Complex</i> :						
Value calculated for $\text{La}(\text{H}_{22}\text{C}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{O}_6)\text{Cl}$	16.85%	46.57%	10.18%	2.66%	7.76%	4.30%
Value observed	16.78%	46.51%	10.08%	2.67%	7.74%	4.28%
2. <i>Cerium Complex</i> :						
Value calculated for $\text{Ce}(\text{H}_{22}\text{C}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{O}_6)\text{Cl}$	16.95%	46.51%	10.17%	2.66%	7.75%	4.29%
Value observed	16.86%	46.50%	10.16%	2.67%	7.68%	4.26%
3. <i>Praseodymium Complex</i> :						
Value calculated for $\text{Pr}(\text{H}_{22}\text{C}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{O}_6)\text{Cl}$	17.08%	46.46%	10.16%	2.66%	7.74%	4.29%
Value observed	16.98%	46.45%	10.14%	2.68%	7.68%	4.28%
4. <i>Neodymium Complex</i> :						
Value calculated for $\text{Nd}(\text{H}_{22}\text{C}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{O}_6)\text{Cl}$	17.35%	46.29%	10.12%	2.65%	7.71%	4.28%
Value observed	17.28%	46.28%	10.08%	2.66%	7.69%	4.28%
5. <i>Samarium Complex</i> :						
Value calculated for $\text{Sm}(\text{H}_{22}\text{C}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{O}_6)\text{Cl}$	17.95%	45.96%	10.00%	2.63%	7.66%	4.25%
Value observed	17.97%	46.93%	9.98%	2.65%	7.69%	4.24%
6. <i>Gadolinium Complex</i> :						
Value calculated for $\text{Gd}(\text{H}_{22}\text{C}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{O}_6)\text{Cl}$	18.63%	45.57%	9.97%	2.61%	7.59%	4.21%
Value observed	18.62%	46.51%	9.96%	2.63%	7.58%	4.21%
7. <i>Dysprosium Complex</i> :						
Value calculated for $\text{Dy}(\text{H}_{22}\text{C}_{32}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{O}_6)\text{Cl}$	19.10%	45.28%	9.90%	2.59%	7.54%	4.18%
Value observed	19.05%	45.24%	9.88%	2.61%	7.54%	4.17%

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Congo red forms 1 : 1 complexes with the chlorides of La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, and Dy which is substantiated by the result of both direct and reverse conductometric titrations.

The formation of 1 : 1 complexes may be explained on the basis of the replacement of two sodium atoms of the disodium salt of the ligand (Congo red) by a trivalent rare-earth ion to give a closed packed structure. The highly soluble nature of the ligand and the insoluble nature of the complex in water medium further support the above view. On the basis of the above results the formula of the complexes may be suggested as $(\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S}_2\text{O}_6)\text{MCl}$ where M stands for La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, and Dy.